

Supplementary Data 7: Interpretation

- a) Cat management study: example 'crib sheet' used for interpretation of Factor 1
- b) Ammunition study: full factor descriptions
- c) Cat management study: full factor descriptions
- d) Translocation study: full factor descriptions

S7a: Cat management study: example 'crib sheet' used for interpretation of Factor 1

Factor 1

+6 Items

- 11* Keeping cats indoors keeps them safe
- 33 I worry about roaming cats being lost, stolen, or killed by traffic

Ranked highest cf. other factors

- 3* If my cat was killed when roaming, I would feel guilty that I hadn't prevented it (+5)
- 8* Choosing to keep cats indoors is fine as long as the owner provides a lot of stimulation (+5)
- 27 Cats should be allowed out but it's OK to keep them in at night (+5)
- 4 Cats that are brought up indoors are used to it (+4)
- 32 I worry that roaming cats are at risk of being deliberately hurt by people (+4)
- 36* I worry about diseases that roaming cats could pick up (+3)
- 37* I worry that foxes will attack cats that are out at night (+3)
- 44 Some cats would prefer to be indoors (+2)
- 19 If you spend enough time with your cat, it can make a difference to the amount it hunts (0) (=F4)
- 22 When there are baby birds around, cats should be kept indoors or in restricted areas of gardens (0)
- 52 It's straightforward to make a garden secure and cat proof (-2) (=F5)
- 17 Cats should be kept indoors to stop them hunting (-4)

Ranked lowest cf. other factors

- 45 Quick-release collars are no use because cats regularly lose them (-4)
- 48 Collars with bells are bad for a cat's mental wellbeing (-4) (=F5)
- 54 Cats hunting is just a nuisance (-4)
- 43 Their hunting is the least attractive part of cat ownership (-3)
- 1 I am concerned that being indoors doesn't give cats the stimulation they need (-3)
- 40 I would be more inclined to manage my cat's hunting behaviour if it was killing stuff all the time (-2)
- 35 Having to deal with prey that cats bring home is disgusting (-2) (=F2)
- 7 Cats help to keep rodent populations down (-1)
- 47* The benefits to cats of going outside outweigh the risks of them getting injured or lost (-1)
- 15* It is natural for cats to want to go out into the world; if they happen to fall foul of it, that's also natural (0)
- 10 I can understand some people being anti-cat because of their hunting behaviour (0) (=F3)
- 25 If there was scientific evidence saying 'this species is endangered because of cats', I would take managing my cats' hunting behaviour much more seriously (0) (=F2)
- 50 Cats should have the right to roam where they please, like a wild animal (0)
- 24 Cats should be able to have the sun shining on their faces, to explore grass, to hunt insects and mice (+1)

-6 Items

- 46* Cats do not belong in the house
- 57 Keeping cats indoors is cruel

S7b: Ammunition study: full factor descriptions

Full descriptions can be found in the relevant paper here:

Newth, J. L., Lawrence, A., Cromie, R. L., Swift, J. A., Rees, E. C., Wood, K. A., ... & McDonald, R. A. (2019). Perspectives of ammunition users on the use of lead ammunition and its potential impacts on wildlife and humans. *People and Nature*, 1(3), 347-361.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/pan3.30>

S7c: Cat management study: full factor descriptions

Reduced versions of these descriptions can be found in the published version here:

Crowley, S. L., Cecchetti, M., & McDonald, R. A. (2020). Diverse perspectives of cat owners indicate barriers to and opportunities for managing cat predation of wildlife. *Frontiers in Ecology and the Environment*, 18(10), 544-549. <https://doi.org/10.1002/fee.2254>

Factor 1:

Factor 1 has an eigenvalue of 8.64 and explains 15.43% of the study variance. 13 participants are significantly associated with this factor. 3 participants kept their cats indoors, 1 was contained (e.g. with fencing or a 'catio'), 6 regulated their cats' outdoor access and 3 had different rules for different cats. None allowed all of their cats unrestricted outdoor access. 6 reported that their cats hunted; 7 reported that they did not. 3 reported managing their cats' hunting; 5 said they did not.

Cat safety is a key concern. These owners worry about roaming cats being lost, stolen or killed by traffic (33*, +6) and if their pet was killed when roaming, they'd feel guilty they hadn't prevented it (3*, +5). Owners are also concerned that roaming cats are at risk of being hurt by people, diseases, and other animals such as foxes (32, +4; 36*, +3, 37*, +3). Keeping cats indoors is a means of keeping them safe (11*, +6), whether just overnight or all the time (27, +5), and is acceptable as long as owners provide enough stimulation (8*, +5; 1, -3; 57, -6). Cats that are brought up indoors, or with restricted outdoor access, get used to this (4, +4) and some might even prefer to be inside (44, +2). These owners are not convinced that the benefits of going outside outweigh the risks of their cats getting injured or lost (47*, -1; 15*, 0).

These owners don't feel particularly strongly about hunting behaviour (55*, +1; 9, +1; 5, -1; 31, -1; 7, -1). They don't find hunting a nuisance (54, -4), tend to believe it is just 'what cats do' (34, +3), and do not think cats should be kept indoors just to stop them hunting (17, -4). However, they don't have any issues with using collars (45, -4; 48, -4) or restricting cats' access to the outdoors in general.

Key Quotes:

"We haven't had children at this point and she is like our child, we love her to bits. We do worry about her to make sure she is safe." (C06)

"They are great company and a big part of family life... And because they are a part of the family, one worries about them." (C11)

"I think it's okay to keep them in at night because it helps obviously with hunting and it keeps them safe, and certainly during the winter months it keeps them nice and warm and cosy." (C13)

"I have never ever let my cats out at night, ever. It's because of the risk to them, I mean most RTAs happen at night or dusk through to night and because I want to know when I go to bed that my cats are safe. I don't want – but then I think of them as being part of the family, they are not just the cat." (D32)

"Hunting is the least attractive part of cat ownership... No, it's not in my opinion because, well I've got cats that are indoors. So actually, the least attractive part is cleaning up after them because they're messy bastards." (G43)

"I am a person who keeps cats indoors. It's my opinion that I feel it's safe for them. And I don't feel like they're missing out on anything. I don't feel like they're stressed, too stressed out. I feel like I give them enough stimulation so that they don't get bored easily." (M46)

"I do have foxes at the back of me. Hear them all night. Maybe one of the reasons why we decide to keep our cats in overnight is because of that." (M47)

“They do enjoy hunting and if you look at them when they are out hunting you can see that they are enjoying it. On the other hand I'd rather have a cat indoors with me because I'm selfish and I like playing with them and I find very comforting. Being a breeder I think that it's very important that my cats don't go out so that they can't be exposed to anything that might make them ill when they go to another home.” (S36)

“Keeping cats indoors I don't think is cruel. And that comes with the stimulation on the other side. I think they need a lot of attention if you keep them indoors. But a lot of mine have been happy, some of them are not happy being kept indoors... I say it's [about the] individuality of the cat.” (S37)

Factor 2:

Factor 2 has an eigenvalue of 8.33 and explains 14.88% of the study variance. 12 participants are significantly associated with this factor. 10 participants allowed their cats unrestricted access to the house and outdoors, or had outdoor (farm) cats; one regulated their cat's access to the house, and one had different rules for different cats. All 12 reported that their cats hunted; none reported managing their pets' hunting behaviour.

Cats' freedom is a priority. These owners believe cats should be able to roam where they please, like a wild animal (50*, +6) and have plenty of outdoor experiences (24*, +6). They are concerned that being kept inside doesn't provide cats the stimulation they need (1, +5; 8, -4), and might even be cruel (57, +2). They are not convinced that cats should be kept in at night (27, -2), or that cats brought up indoors get used to this (4*, -2). Compared with the other perspectives, they are least concerned about their cats being at risk due to their roaming behaviour (33, +1; 3, 0; 32, +1; 36, 0; 37, 0), and believe the benefits of roaming outweigh the potential costs (47, +4; 15, +3).

Hunting is perceived as broadly positive because it helps control rodent populations (7, +4; 31, +2) and is a sign of a normal, healthy and comfortable cat (49, +5; 29, +3). Consequently, owners tend not to be bothered by hunting (5, +2) and may even be proud of their cats' hunting prowess (28, +2). They are opposed to any restrictions on roaming and hunting behaviour, including bans on cat ownership (14, -5) and keeping cats inside (17, -6; 22, -5). They think that owners can't stop their cats hunting (55, +3), and don't think they have a responsibility to manage their pets' hunting behaviour (60, -4; 53, +4).

Key Quotes:

“I think that I'm comfortable with the fact that my cat goes hunting, if anything I am somewhat proud that he does. I think it's a good thing that they are able to go out and catch pests... and whilst I do worry somewhat about him getting hurt outside of the house I think that the benefits outweigh the costs... And I just think cats are part of the ecosystem.” (B24)

“We do know that they get stressed if they're shut indoors.” (C07)

“I just think it's really cruel to keep a cat indoors. So yeah for just because it's the circle of life anyway. It's natural for them to do it.” (C10)

“[[I'm] definitely pro outdoor cats. Pro my cat being allowed to do whatever she wants. And being able to catch mice and stuff it's just what they do naturally...” (C10)

“I like to have cats that are out free doing what they want to do. If they catch animals great, if they don't that's fine as well.” (C12)

“I think they are wild. I've seen cats that have been inside for many years and they suddenly go outside and they normally thrive and love it. So I've got experience of indoor cats loving outdoors.” (C12)

“Cats are wild here, they're born outside and they'll kill things if they want to kill things I guess... the farm cats yeah. I think they're wild.” (C39)

"I think if a cat wants to hunt then you should let it hunt if it's safe I guess. Cats help keep rodent populations down, here that's a big yes they do, they'll kill rats and rabbits and mice and voiles and all sorts of things around hedges." (C39)

"I think the take home message is as I said cats need to be able to go outside. I think it's cruel to keep them indoors." (C41)

"I think yes there has been a decline in garden birds but I genuinely don't think you can lay that at the cat's door." (C41)

"My view is sort of saying that cats will hunt, you can't stop them. They love the wildlife. You shouldn't have a cat if you're going to keep it indoors I don't think. I think they are animals that need to be outside. And that it's nature, it's what happens really." (D34)

"I have thought of putting a bell on the collar when she's brought the birds in but then because we're overrun with mice I'd rather think that she's getting rid of some of the vermin that's around." (M51)

"I think cats should be allowed to go out, hunt and do what cats do." (M55)

"I do worry that they're going to get hurt or injured. But how much my cats enjoy being outside and I'd rather they had that for a shorter period of time if that's what it was than be stuck in a house for their entire lives." (M56)

"I think that any animal you have should be treated as an honoured guest and you should give it the best and most natural life that you can do. So, you know, keeping them in and making them live in permanently I find is a very uncomfortable idea." (S35)

Factor 3:

Factor 3 has an eigenvalue of 7.43 and explains 13.28% of the study variance. 12 participants were significantly associated with this factor. 6 owners allowed their cats unrestricted access to the house and outdoors; 5 regulated their cats' outdoor access; and one contained their cat within a restricted area. 8 reported that their cats hunted; 4 that they did not. 7 did not manage their cats' hunting; 1 did.

Cats should have outdoor access (24; +4; 58, +1; 50, +2), though overnight confinement is acceptable (27, +3) and these owners wouldn't want an 'outdoor only' cat (38, +6). On balance, these owners feel the benefits of roaming outweigh the potential risks (47, +5; 15, +3; 3, 0), but they do worry about their cats' safety while roaming (33, +3; 32, +2).

Hunting is considered the least attractive aspect of cat ownership (43*, +3); owners dislike their pets hunting (28, -6; 31, -4; 5, -3; 35, +1) and make concerted efforts to rescue prey their cats bring home (42*, +6). They love wildlife and don't like the idea of their cats' causing any animal to suffer (39, +4; 21, -3), but feel strongly that hunting is just 'what cats do' (34, +5). While they may be inclined to make more of an effort to manage hunting behaviour if their cat started hunting prolifically (40, +3), they don't know how owners can effectively reduce hunting (61, -4; 56, +1; 20, 0; 19, -1) without restricting roaming, which they are unwilling to do (17, -5; 22, -3).

Key Quotes:

"I do think cats should be allowed to go outdoors, I do think it's cruel unless there's reasons for them to be kept indoors. I think they're an animal and that's natural for them. It does upset me when they kill other things but so does general wildlife, everything kills everything else really in nature doesn't it?" (B18)

"I think that hunting is a natural cat behaviour. I think it's very difficult to control it. There are quite possibly some things that can be done. I mean people do try to and a lot of people feel quite strongly about cats hunting so maybe if there is some responsibility if you are a cat owner to try and moderate its behaviour but you can't really moderate its behaviour you can

only restrict its access I think. And that I think is where the difficulty can come into it, is the appropriateness of doing that" (B26)

"I wouldn't be proud of it, if it hunted it hunted, that's fine it's a cat and some of them hunt and some of them don't but I wouldn't sort of think 'Oh that's my boy' you know what I mean?" (B26)

"I don't think that anything killing anything else is something to be proud of to be honest." (B28)

"It's not that I want my cats to hunt, I don't want my cat to be cruel to other animals ... but I do think it's a nature thing and the fact is if you invite a feline into your home you have to accept that they're going to want to go out, they're going to want to hunt. If my cat was a more prolific hunter I would certainly try and do something to stop it. Mostly because I don't want another animal to suffer at the hands of my animal just because I like having a cat around." (B28)

"I'm a real supporter of wildlife but hunting is just a natural behaviour for cats I think." (C01)

"I hate it when she hunts and she does it quite frequently." (C04)

"if your cats do go outside then it's not for you to limit their hunting instinct but rather to protect local wildlife, particularly the baby birds at that time of year as much as you can. I don't think people should keep their cats inside just so they don't hunt." (C16)

"I think that all animals have the right to be themselves really. Although it's not a nice aspect of having a cat if they do hunt it is natural and they've got as much right to be out and about for their own mental health as birds." (M44)

"I've got one cat...who brings in things but it only tends to be in summer and it's baby birds. And then it's few and far between... I don't like it, I'm not happy about it but there's not a lot I can do about it. He's got a collar ...He's so quick... there's just nothing you can do about it." (M50)

"It's not just birds, I would be concerned about any animal or creature. I would be just as unhappy if they caught mice or other things that I don't really like. Moths." (M52)

"I will always rescue. Even if it's something I hate." (M52)

"I would never say [hunting] was a good sign of anything because I don't think it is. It's not good. I mean yes I suppose it is natural, showing natural behaviour but they can show that as well in other ways." (M52)

Factor 4

Factor 4 has an eigenvalue of 4.52 and explains 8.06% of the study variance. 7 participants were significantly associated with this factor. 6 allowed their cats unregulated access to the house and outdoors; 1 had different rules for different cats. 6 reported that their cats hunted; 1 that they did not. 4 reported managing their cats' hunting; 2 did not.

From this perspective cats should have outdoor access (58, +4; 24, +4), but owners didn't express strong opposition to keeping them indoors, either permanently or just at night (57, +1; 4, 0; 27, 0). They did worry about their cats while roaming (33, +3), but believed that the benefits of this outweighed the risks (15, +4; 47, +2).

Owners are bothered by their cats' hunting behaviour, however (5, -5) and are particularly concerned about cats' potential impacts on garden birds (6, +6; 21*, +5). They have thought seriously about the issue of cat predation on wildlife (2, -5; 9, -4), believe that even a single cat could be harmful (12, -4), and are aware of other people's concerns about this issue (10, +3). They are the most likely to believe that owners have some responsibility to manage hunting behaviour (60, +2; 53, 0) and the most confident about how to approach this (61, +1; 56, +3), though they still expressed uncertainty about the effectiveness of different methods (19, 0; 52, -5). They would be further inclined to manage hunting in the face of compelling

scientific evidence of specific impacts (25, +4) or if they had a voracious hunter (40, +5). This perspective is least opposed to restrictions on cat ownership (14, -1), but doesn't think cats should be kept inside to stop them hunting (17, -6; 22, -2).

Key Quotes:

"Maybe I could do more so maybe it's something to think about but I'd be thinking about it more if she'd hunted and I think the last thing she caught was a slowworm and that was about two years ago. But I did not enjoy the hunting, I'd rather sort of deal with poo or sick or anything else." (B19)

"It was sparrows and blackbirds and the tail of a magpie and a racing pigeon and just awful things. And it's really upsetting and it's horrible and especially when they're alive but obviously so injured that they're not going to recover... But my current ones, we've had in the four years maybe a couple of birds just but mice it's like loads of mice... With rats and mice I absolutely don't care how much suffering they inflict and I just want them dead." (B27)

"One of them was about the cat collars with bells ... I'm hoping that in some ways they hear the cat coming and they think, oh hey rather than it creeping up." (B29)

"One cat can't do much harm to wildlife by itself and I disagree with that because one cat can do a lot of harm, it can, that's what I feel." (B29)

"I don't think it's something anyone should encourage even though it's probably a natural behaviour. But equally because it is a natural behaviour and being outside is natural for cats I don't think we should keep them inside to stop them hunting. If you feel that strongly about it that you should keep them inside then a cat is not the pet for you." (C05)

"If you do let your cat go outside it's your responsibility to make sure your cat is a good citizen. I understand that hunting is a natural behaviour but I'm very sure there are ways you can discourage that or collars and things like that to try and help." (C05)

"I always had the feeling that they should be outdoors in the sunshine, it's an animal, I don't like it being kept inside. But there is a bit of a paradox in that, they do hunt, and I don't mind them killing mice and rats, I quite like that because we had a bit of a rat problem in our fields back along but I don't like them hunting birds." (C08)

"I don't like it catching sparrows because I know they're vulnerable." (C08)

"I do care considerably about mitigating my cats hunting, not ability but hunting habit. The next bullet point would be but other than using a collar with a bell on it I wouldn't necessarily know how to go about that in any other way." (C42)

"I think they probably are having an impact on bird life. How much, don't know. Certainly in the urban areas." (M49)

Factor 5

Factor 5 has an eigenvalue of 2.90 and explains 5.18% of the study variance. 3 participants were significantly associated with this factor. 2 allowed their cats unrestricted access to the house and the outdoors; 1 regulated access. 1 reported their cat hunting; 2 that they did not. No owners managed their cats' hunting.

Owners don't strongly advocate either outdoor access or keeping cats indoors. They don't think keeping cats indoors is cruel (57, -3) or that cats must have outdoor access (58, -1) but do think they benefit from being outdoors (47, +3). They worry that their cats might be lost, stolen or killed by traffic (33, +5), but perceive these risks as natural for outdoor cats (15, +4) and are not concerned about more specific threats such as diseases or people causing their pets deliberate harm (32, -3; 36, -4).

When they got a cat, these owners didn't really think about whether it would hunt (9, +4), and they've never seriously thought about the effect of cats on wildlife populations (2, +6). Because they've hardly considered it, they have no strong feelings about hunting behaviour

(5, +1; 43, +1; 49, 0; 31, 0), but they don't like the idea of their cat causing other animals to suffer (39, +3) and would be more inclined to manage hunting if their cat was a big hunter (40, +6) or if there were evidence of specific wildlife impacts (25, +5). They don't think cats should be kept inside to stop them hunting (17, -5) but see belled collars as an effective and low-risk means of managing hunting behaviour (56, +4; 30, -6; 48, -4).

Key Quotes:

"I worry about the effect of cats hunting on garden bird populations... it's just never ever crossed my mind and my cats have not brought a bird in so that's probably why... There wasn't cause to cross my mind, I didn't think about hunting when I got the cats and they've never had a bird" (B21)

"Hunting is not really a big issue for me. That might change because my cats are just two and we've only had the one bird incident and I've never really given much consideration to it. And I think I'd want my cats to be in and outdoors but I think cats need exercise like human beings do, I wouldn't want my cat inside all the time it would drive me nuts so just a little bit every now and again is fine." (B21)

"So I'm not a kind of right on rights cat person, they're a bit of extra company and I do worry about them being killed because it's not very nice. But if it happens then we'd all be a bit sad but it means that when we go away at the weekend we wouldn't have to find someone to feed the cats. So it's not the end of the world. We haven't brought them into this world, I wouldn't go looking for a pedigree. Rescue cats it's fine, we've got cats, I don't how long they'll be with us. So they're lovely but I don't really take them that seriously." (B21)

"I have to say I hadn't really thought about the hunting and killing aspect. She doesn't really kill anything because she's quite a wary little cat but I know other cats do and I've had cats all my life and they kill stuff and I've never really thought about it." (C17)

"I honestly wouldn't be able to tell you how many cats are in the UK, there's probably a lot and the percentage of those that actually go out and kill wildlife I would have thought it's kill or be killed out there isn't it?" (C17)

"As long as you get the quick release collar then they shouldn't be dangerous and I think they're important to show and have the tag on with the cat's address and everything." (C17)

"I think I would if say there was a rare species of bird or something in the area then I would take it more seriously. [Is he much of a hunter?] No not at all. As far as I'm aware because I don't know everything but he doesn't go out at night and he goes out for five minutes." (M53)

"So if my cat was a hunter then I would put a collar with a bell on it for sure, I think that does help." (M53)

S7d: Translocation study: full factor descriptions

Full factor descriptions are found in the relevant paper here:

Bavin, D., MacPherson, J., Denman, H., Crowley, S. L., & McDonald, R. A. (2020). Using Q-methodology to understand stakeholder perspectives on a carnivore translocation. *People and Nature*, 2(4), 1117-1130. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pan3.10139>